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Assessment of the applicability of composite mechanical test standards for use with 3D woven composites

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Introduction - Background

- 2D composites
 - Reinforced along in-plane directions
 - Weaker through-thickness properties
- 3D composites
 - Reinforcement in the through-thickness direction
 - Improves interlaminar/ through-thickness strength
 - Unit cell of 3D composites often $>$ 2D woven composites
 - Larger volume of material may be required to represent the bulk material during testing
 - Through-thickness reinforcement may influence the mode of failure during testing

Q: Are current mechanical test standards fit for purpose with regards to 3D composites?

Introduction - Background (cont.)

- Many different types of 3D composite, each defined by the through-thickness reinforcing structure

Project aims

1. To assess the suitability of various mechanical test standards for composite materials for two types of 3D woven architectures
 2. To provide recommendations on the use of different test standards with regards to 3D composites
- Future work will aim to develop test methods that would be more appropriate for use with these material structures

Materials

	Glass-fibre	Carbon-fibre
Weaver	Axis composites	Sigmatex
Z-binder structure	Orthogonal	Layer-to-layer
No. of warp layers	5	7
No. of weft layers	6	8
Tex of all tows (g/km)	1200	800
Areal density (gsm)	3330	5300
Warp unit cell (mm)	~10	16.9
Weft unit cell (mm)	~10	9.6
Approx. composite thickness (mm)	3	5
Resin	Epoxy	Epoxy
Fibre volume fraction, V_f (%)	37.3 ± 1.5	65.2 ± 0.6
Void volume fraction, V_v (%)	0.01 ± 0.27	0.80 ± 0.06
Panel manufacture	Combined vacuum bag resin infusion with low pressure autoclave cure	

3D GFRP Orthogonal Weave

3D CFRP Layer-to-layer (LTL) weave

Test Matrix

Test Method	Test Standard	Geometry flexibility	Specimen dimensions and variations
Compression	ISO 14126	Some	$L_1 = 110\text{mm}$, $L_2 = 125\text{mm}$; $W_1 = 10\text{mm}$, $W_2 = 25\text{mm}$, $W_3 = 36\text{mm}$; $GL = 10\text{mm}/ 25\text{mm}$
	ASTM D3410	Yes	$L = 120\text{mm}$; $W_1 = 25\text{mm}$, $W_2 = 36\text{mm}$; $GL = 20\text{mm}$
Compression (Open-hole)	ISO 12817	Yes	$L_1 = 118\text{mm}$; $L_2 = 125\text{mm}$ $W_1 = 24\text{mm} - \text{Ø}4\text{mm}$; $W_2 = 36\text{mm} - \text{Ø}6\text{mm}$; $GL = 18\text{mm}/ 25\text{mm}$
Compression after impact	ISO 18352	No	$L = 150 \text{ mm}$; $W = 100\text{mm}$
4-point bending	ISO 14125	Yes	Lengths between = $30t$ and $50t$; Spans between $22.5t$ and $40.5t$
Mode I	ISO 15024	No	$L = 150\text{mm}$; $W = 20\text{mm}$; Starter crack = 60mm
	ASTM D5528	Yes	$L = 150\text{mm}$; $W = 20\text{mm}$; Starter crack = 60mm
Mode II	ISO 15114	Some	$L = 190\text{mm}$; $W = 20\text{mm}$; Starter crack = 60mm
± 45 tension	ISO 14129	Some	$L = 250\text{mm}$; $W_1 = 25\text{mm}$, $W_2 = 35\text{mm}$
Short beam shear	ISO 14130	Yes	$L = 10t$; $W = 5t$
	ASTM D2344	Yes	$L = 6t$; $W = 2t$
V-notch	ASTM D5379	No	Standard dimensions $L = 76\text{mm}$; $W = 19\text{mm}$; Notch $W = 11.4\text{mm}$
Tension	ISO 527-4	Some	$L = 250\text{mm}$; $W_1 = 25\text{mm}$, $W_2 = 35\text{mm}$
Tension (Open-hole)	ASTM D7332	Some	$L = 250\text{mm}$; $W_1 = 24\text{mm} - \text{Ø}4\text{mm}$, $W_2 = 36\text{mm} - \text{Ø}6\text{mm}$, $W_3 = 48\text{mm} - \text{Ø}8\text{mm}$

Measurement of strain

Material architectures with large unit cell areas can result in a large variance in strains measured depending on the area covered. Larger gauge area = smaller uncertainty in measurements

GFRP Orthogonal specimen loaded in compression along the warp direction Stress: 230MPa

Gauge [mm]	2x2	4x4	6x6	10x10	15x15	24x15
E [GPa]	21.13	19.14	17.58	16.98	17.14	17.06

Compression

- Compression test results shown here were acquired through the use of the end-loading method outlined in ISO 14126
- Due to specimen thickness GFRP and CFRP specimens were tested with a 10mm and 25mm gauge-section, respectively
- Modulus values measured using a virtual strain gauge covering most of the visible specimen gauge area
- Failure modes observed in agreement with acceptable failure modes outlined in the ISO 14126

ISO 14126

Compression

CFRP specimens near failure show many repeating regions of low strain, indicating that some regions carry little load throughout.

Warp direction loading

Position of z-binder crowns

Weft direction loading

ISO 14126

Tension

ISO 527-4

Open-hole testing

- Open-hole tension (OHT) and compression (OHC) tests were conducted according to ASTM D5766 and ISO 12817, respectively
- OHT and OHC - similar range of notched to unnotched strength loss covered by all directions and materials tested
- Tension strength loss slightly less than compression
- In tension, glass-fibre material performs better than carbon-fibre material
- In compression, weft direction generally performs better

Shear

- Shear properties measured using 3 different test methods
 - Short beam shear
 - V-notch
 - $\pm 45^\circ$ Tension
- Repeatability of each test is good for both shear strength and modulus measurements
- Noticeable difference in measured properties between each test method
 - Increased coupon size = increase in measured properties

Test method	Shear plane
SBS	1-3
V-notch	1-2
$\pm 45^\circ$ Tension	1-2

Shear – observed failure

Short beam shear	V-notch	$\pm 45^\circ$
<p>GFRP failure is generally found to be a combination of interlaminar shear failure and tensile cracking along the specimen underside – considered unacceptable by testing standards.</p> <p>CFRP failure is similar to GFRP, but also has possible compressive failure.</p>	<p>Failure mode appears consistent with the acceptable failure modes within ASTM D5379</p> <p>Combination of cracking modes (shown below) were observed to have developed within the gauge-section between notches.</p>	<p>During loading, transverse matrix cracks developed at numerous points in GFRP specimens. Development of this damage through continued loading lead to eventual separation along a 45° path between tows.</p> <p>In CFRP LTL specimens, extreme scissoring of fibre tows was observed, providing an almost necking type effect until the test is stopped.</p>

GFRP Warp

CFRP Warp

GFRP Warp

CFRP Warp

GFRP±45

CFRP±45

Flexure

GFRP Orthogonal

- Weft tows at surface
- Warp tows below surface
- Low spans: clear interlaminar shear failure
- Large spans: limited interlaminar shear failure and very high deflections

Damage includes: transverse matrix cracking and z-binder debonding, interlaminar shear failure along longitudinal tows

Flexure

GFRP Orthogonal

- Reduced strength with increased span length
- Modulus – high scatter, but generally minimal change with increasing span length
- Indicates that this test method may be appropriate for measuring flexural modulus, but not for strength

Flexure

Outer span = 206mm

CFRP LTL – warp direction

- Similar damage to orthogonal weave, i.e. matrix cracking, interlaminar failure even at long span lengths.
- Additionally kink band failure on longitudinal tows

Mode I – fracture toughness GFRP Orthogonal weave

- CFRP tabs used to increase arm bending stiffness and aid crack propagation
- Crack growth was relatively stable initially
- Followed by preferential crack growth along the top of the specimen near tabbed region
- Limited crack growth along desired path

60mm slot cut using a diamond wire saw

Mode I – fracture toughness CFRP LTL weave

- Fairly stable crack propagation from starter crack with obvious stick-slip type behaviour
- Lots of crack branching due to the material architecture
- Clear fibre bridging – weft tows
- Crack growth along “desired” path

60mm long slot machined
using a diamond wire saw

Mode I – fracture toughness CFRP LTL weave

Plane 1

Plane 2

Plane 3

Conclusions and recommendations

- Throughout this project numerous testing standards have been used to assess their applicability with regards to 3D composites. From this work, many interesting observations have been made, including:
 - For 3D composites with large unit cells, DIC is useful for observing the complex loadings
 - Recommended as an initial method for determining effective coverage area required for bulk strain measurements
 - Under compressive loading, the area in which strain is measured can affect modulus measurements, especially since gauge lengths are often small
 - Loss of strength via OHT and OHC testing, results in a similar range of loss covered by both material architectures.

Conclusions and recommendations

- When shear loading a specimen in accordance with different shear test standards, the magnitude of the same measured properties can be vastly different, despite having acceptable failure modes, i.e. V-notch and $\pm 45^\circ$ tension. Short beam shear tests produce unacceptable failure modes.
- Four-point flexure testing appears to provide relatively consistent moduli, but determination of strength needs consideration due to the development of interlaminar shear failures.
- DCB testing for mode I fracture toughness is not recommended with 3D composites due to the influence of the through-thickness reinforcement on the crack propagation through the material, i.e. large scale crack branching, fibre bridging.

Questions?

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